

No pre-treatment differences (24 hr pre; $P > 0.05$) occurred among groups when comparing the number of either small or large follicles (2.95 ± 0.8 vs. 3.02 ± 0.3), respectively. Besides, no post-treatment differences (24 hr post; $P > 0.05$) occurred among groups regarding number of small follicles (GC, 3.0 ± 0.1 ; G54, 2.7 ± 0.1 and G84, 3.0 ± 0.1). Nonetheless, while no differences occurred in number of large follicles between the G54 (7.5 ± 0.9) and G84 (6 ± 0.8) groups at 48 hr post, the GC depicted no large follicle population ($P < 0.05$) 48 hr post (d0). Results suggest that two doses of GnRH in P4-primed goats enhanced follicular growth (i.e. large follicles) during the breeding season.

P111 | Successful vitrification of hybrid (*Bos taurus* ♀ x *Bison bonasus* ♂) embryos

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Wisent (*Bison bonasus*) is a protected species in Europe. One of the latest trends in Wisent protection is the usage of assisted reproductive technologies. Hybrid embryos are a useful model for establishing the methodology of in vitro wisent embryo production and vitrification. The aim of the study was to evaluate the quality of hybrid embryos (*Bos taurus* ♀ x *Bison bonasus* ♂) after vitrification. Cumulus-oocyte complexes (COC) were isolated from cattle (*Bos Taurus*) ovaries and matured in TCM 199 with 10% FBS, 0.02 IU NIH-pFSH/ml, 1 µg/ml β-estradiol, 0.2 mM Na pyruvate, and antibiotics for 24 hr at 38.5°C and 5% CO₂ in humidified air. Sperm from a wisent bull (*Bison bonasus*) had previously been isolated from the epididymis of wisent culled out of reproductive season, and subsequently frozen. Thawed spermatozoa were used for in vitro fertilization of matured COC in TL medium with 6 mg/ml BSA FAF, 0.2 mM sodium pyruvate, 20 µM penicillamine, 10 µM hypotaurine, 1 µM epinephrine, 2 µg/ml heparin and antibiotics. The hybrid embryos were co-cultured with Vero cells into SOF with 10% FBS and antibiotics for 7 days at 38.5°C under 5% CO₂ in humidified air. After 168 hr, only 11 hybrid embryos (4 morulae and 7 early blastocysts out of total 16 embryos obtained (68.75%) and the total oocytes used (21.57%)) were vitrified and thawed according to BOVIPRO Vit-Kit™ procedures. The morphology of vitrified and thawed hybrid embryos was evaluated under microscope based on a modification

of the IETS manual for cattle. After vitrification, all hybrid embryos preserved their good quality (G1 based on modified IETS manual for cattle). In conclusion hybrid embryos (*Bos taurus* ♀ x *Bison bonasus* ♂) can be successfully vitrified using BOVIPRO Vit-Kit™ procedures. Granted OR.271.3.10.2017.

P112 | The impact of environmental factors on the immunohematological parameters of pregnant cows

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The aim was to monitor the immunohematological parameters of cow blood at different stages of pregnancy ($n = 697$ Black-mottled Holstein, milk yield/year 8540 ± 121.64 kg) in environmentally unfavorable conditions (elevated Pb, Cd, Fe, Cu, Zn, Cr) of the Sverdlovsk region for the period 2012–2018. This region is well-known for its intensive heavy metal industry. Hematological parameters were analyzed on an Abacus junior Vet analyzer, and immunological parameters were determined according to generally accepted methods. Anemia was observed in varying degrees of severity, accentuated in the second half of pregnancy: the hemoglobin concentration was 83.50 ± 3.41 g/L. Concerning composition of leukocytes, a shift to an increase in stab neutrophils by 23%, eosinophils and monocytes by 5%, and a shift in segmented neutrophils and lymphocytes to the upper limit of the physiological norm [1]. The number of phagocytic cells amounted to $52.05 \pm 5.04\%$. The relative content of T-lymphocytes decreased to $39.50 \pm 4.15\%$, B-lymphocytes to $25.05 \pm 2.14\%$. T and B lymphocytes were determined by flow cytometry (FacsCanto II, «Becton Dickinson»). The leukocyte-T-lymphocytic index in pregnant cows was in the range of 4.80–7.04 units, which corresponds to the normoergic state and indicates the absence of autoimmune and immunodeficiency states. The recorded changes in red and white blood cells reflect a high level of adaptive reactions to adverse environmental factors during pregnancy. [1] Vasiliev et al., Vet Clin Hematol: A training Manual, 2015.

P113 | Polymerase chain reaction in diagnostics of latent and persistent forms of infectious cattle diseases

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PCR was carried out as a diagnosis of biological and pathological material from cattle, from 17 farms located in the Ural region. We studied biological samples from cows with a decreased milk